

Profit and Loss Statements

By Edwin Amuga

Abstract

Project management mainly aims to eliminate risks and improve service delivery. It is important to take into consideration project and corporate accounting when making project management decisions. For this reason, project managers need to have a basic understanding of key financial statements of a business and how each project affects the statement. This helps in the betterment of communication and cooperation between the financial departments and the project management professionals of a business. This also helps in making better decisions regarding to project management. This paper approaches an overview and explanation of key financial statements including the balance sheet, the cash flow statement and the income statement. It also gives a brief overview of key words of earned value management. The paper also gives brief examples on the effects of a project on each financial statement and suggestions on better project management decision making by considering both systems of accounting when making project decisions.

Introduction

Project management as a profession is founded on risk elimination and increasing commodity earnings in the face of ever-increasing money velocity. Project management is housed as a business on government-supported legal entities. Tax payment is one of the legal requirements that governments demand of businesses which is only made possible when money

is earned and profits made (Carnergie 2016). This implies that money making and risk elimination is a primary goal of any business. The government requires businesses to provide financial insights for protection of their legal status of businesses. In light of these, businesses adhere to generally accepted accounting principles in order to meet their tax payment obligations. As a result, businesses create three main financial statements, namely, the balance sheet, the cash flow statement and the income statement. These documents are made from the same accounting data including the general ledger. Each of these named documents has their own purpose which business owners and managements pay attention to and use them to make their business decisions (Iribar and Isabel 2017).

As a profession, project management has its distinguished financial system referred to as the earned value management and most project managers use it to make financial decisions for projects. Most decisions made based on this system is not the most favorable for the three financial statements of a business and as a result, project managers must have a basic understanding of key financial statements and how each affects statements. This is imperative in enhancing corporation and communication between the financial departments and the project managers. This document interchangeably uses the terms accounting systems and financial statements even though they are not the same.

The balance sheet

The balance sheet is described as the snapshot of the business or company as it shows the financial position and health of a company at a particular date. The document organizes and summarizes all ownership of a business and assets and the debts as liabilities and shows the difference between the two as shareholders or owner's equity. In this way, the balance sheet

provides an overview of the company assets value and who owns the assets. All assets are shown on the left while their owners are displayed on the right. Assets encompass everything from buildings, offices, machinery and vehicles and their owners may include the banks that loaned the money to the business and required collateral or assets for loan approval. The document gets its name from the fact that it aims to balance the value of assets and liabilities and the owners' or shareholder's equity.

Balance sheets help business owners, investors and lenders know who owns which assets at what time and also help in generating financial ratios providing financial health insights on which decisions are made (Veraat 2009). Managerial decisions made must favor the ratios and project managers must make themselves aware of the reasons for such decisions.

The income statement

The income statement as a document the periods before and after the balance sheet and conveniently gives the financial performance of a business or company over a time period, commonly in terms over a month, quarter or a year. The income statement is also referred to as the profit and loss statement and the direct expenses as cost of sales and indirect expenses as the overhead costs and revenues. The statement also shows the gross profit, income before tax, income tax and net income (Wu and Xiao 2020). The net income, also known as the bottom line, comes as the last item on the statement. Project-related costs are categorized as direct expenses as they are incurred while creating unique products. Indirect expenses are not related to creation of a new product as they are recurring. Preparation of the income statement is crucial as it lists all expenses the company incurs and shows the financial performance of a business over a time period. In this way, it shows if the company is making profits or losses during the specified

period and can be used to predict future prospects. The cash and non-cash items are also listed on the income statement despite the fact that they may not reflect the actual inflows and outflows of cash during the period. This happens when an uncollected cash sale is recorded in the income statement. The cash flow statement provides information related to cash in hand.

The Cash Flow Statement

As the income statement accesses the financial performance of a company over a specified time period, the cash flow statement tracks the actual cash in hand. The document is different from other financial statements as it does not include future cash inflows and outflows recorded on credit. The document relates to the two above mentioned statements due to the fact that it shows the effects of the changes in the other statements on cash (Carnergie 2016). The Cash flow statement purposely reports the sources and uses of cash during a specified reporting time period. Tracking available cash in the company by the financial department at any given time period is crucial as it is used to prepare the cash flow statement which is in turn used as a planning tool that helps in forecasting and making business and project decisions such as business expansion or taking on a new project or line of business. The document helps in identifying time periods that need borrowing for advance making or arrangements before cash is needed. Lenders and creditors also find the cash flow statement very valuable in assessing the ability of the company to repay.

Financial statement impact on projects

During a project, the activities of project managers affects the same areas on the financial statements as most business transactions such as the revenue, the cost of sales and overhead costs on the income statement and operating activities on the cash flow statement. Project management

effects changes on these headings which also effects changes in certain corporate ratios. The balance sheet consolidates the income statement and the cash flow statement, implying that changes in the two statements impacts the balance sheet and balance sheet ratios as well. A project manager making sales and sending out invoices affects income heading and hence the income statement. Salaries and direct costs related to projects are grouped under direct expenses. In light of these, project managers can liaise with the financial department to positively affect the operating activities in the cash flow statement since a project must have its own cash flows. Project management daily activities link to financial statement in various ways (Wu and Xiao 2020).

Earned Value management, on the other hand is aimed at measuring the performance of a project by integrating the scope, schedule and resources of the project. Earned Value Management as a project management accounting technique is utilized to project and only uses certain accounting tools. The project manager and the project management office analyze the accounting data of the project together and important deviations from the project baseline for making of corrections. The corrections are made based on accounting figures and do not consider the financial statement preferences of a company. Every project implementation impacts the financial health and therefore calls for bridging project accounting and company financial department for general profitability.

Works cited

Carnegie, Garry D. "The accounting professional project and bank failures." *Journal of Management History* (2016).

Iribar, Ainhoa Saitua, and Isabel Vázquez Arias. "Experience in Active Methodologies: Project for Introduction to Accounting and Financial Accounting Subjects in the Grade of Labor Relations and Human Resources of the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) (2017)."

Veraart. Merging project and corporate accounting: is it impossible? Maybe. Paper presented at PMI® Global Congress 2009—North America, Orlando, FL. Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute (2009).

Wu, Yanhong, and Xiao Wang. "Application of Blockchain Technology in the Integration of Management Accounting and Financial Accounting." *The International Conference on Cyber Security Intelligence and Analytics*. Springer, Cham, 2020.